

Governance Legacy and Digitisation in Contextualising Systems Approaches for Local Knowledge and Values Preservation. A Case study of South Africa

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ABSTRACT: This paper explores the correlation between governance practices, contextualised systems approach, and the preservation of local knowledge and values in South Africa. In the context of Agenda 2063 for Africa, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and the global imperative set by the UN, this paper aims to clarify how local knowledge contributes to digitization efforts and its impact on protecting values within governance frameworks. Using a desktop research methodology, this paper brings together existing literature and empirical evidence to examine the challenges encountered by countries in preserving their governance traditions amidst rapid digitalization and evolving global frameworks. The findings highlight the complexity of integrating knowledge systems into a context while aligning with Agenda 2063 aspirations and SDGs. The study's key contribution is that it uses Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH) to embrace digital transformation while keeping governance systems in check. The adaptability of CSH is proven in the South African government, where it has shown effective in maintaining long-standing traditions of good administration. The results support the idea of integrating indigenous knowledge systems with digital techniques, as well as a systems approach that considers local circumstances. The findings of this paper provide suggestions for long-term planning that may help keep local knowledge of good governance alive and well while also contributing to regional and global development goals.

Keywords: governance legacy, local knowledge, African Agenda 2063, digitalization, critical systems heuristics.

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1. Introduction

South Africa and the wider Southern African Development Community (SADC) region are currently engaged in a process of reclaiming and redefining their own governance, culture, and indigenous knowledge, which has been influenced by a history of colonial domination. This narrative explores the resilience of states within the SADC, as well as the rest of Africa, in their efforts to overcome the lasting effects of colonialism and establish their own distinct identities and systems of governance. Academics like Wunsch (2001) have examined the effects of decentralization policies in Africa, while Mann (2017)

has analyzed the political and economic consequences of the Big Data revolution on the continent, highlighting the continued importance of these historical influences.

This article seeks to fill the existing knowledge gap on the connection between post-colonial legacies and the digital era. Its objective is to shed light on how countries in the SADC area might utilize digitalization to promote and safeguard indigenous knowledge and values within their governing structures. This study explores the delicate balance between tradition and technological progress, building on Thinyane and Terzoli's (2009) argument for a digital inclusion that integrates technology into local knowledge systems, going beyond mere connectivity.

Incorporating and preserving their rich, cultural knowledge in the face of the global digital revolution is crucial for the socio-political future of South Africa and the SADC region. This paper examines the relationship between the historical governance practices of post-colonial societies and the process of digitalization. The article specifically examines how post-colonial societies can utilize the digital revolution to protect and preserve local knowledge and cultural values. This paper adds to the discussion on post-colonialism in the African setting, aiming to provide valuable insights that might shape policy-making and strengthen local systems in the face of the widespread digital effect.

2. An overview of digitalization in African countries

Digital technology has significantly changed the approach to governance and social involvement in Africa, particularly in South Africa and the wider Southern African Development Community (SADC) region. Digitalization has reshaped the channels through which the government transmits information and facilitates citizen participation. This is particularly evident in participatory sensing projects in East Africa, which have amplified the voices of citizens and increased their impact on public services (Georgiadou et al., 2011). The rapid advancement of digital technology presents significant opportunities for growth and connectedness. However, it also presents a potential danger to the traditional knowledge systems that form the foundation of the cultural legacy in South Africa and the SADC area.

The dominance of globalized information in the digital sphere poses a threat to the preservation of indigenous knowledge and practices, which could lead to the erosion of African nations' cultural heritages. South Africa, known for its abundant and varied cultural expressions, requires the development of digital platforms that combine contemporary with tradition to save and maintain these cultural heritages (Baud et al., 2014). Additionally, to this paper examine the interaction between well-established governance traditions and knowledge systems techniques in the context of Africa's, particularly South Africa's, digital development (Breuer et al., 2017). Ulrich (2005) came up with Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH), which is a good way to evaluate and change digital projects that are both technologically sound and sensitive to culture. CSH allows for the preservation of the region's traditional ways of running things and cultural identity while implementing digital standards (Ulrich 2012).

This article suggests doing a thorough investigation of the relationship between post-colonial governance legacies and digitalization in South Africa and the Southern African Development Community (SADC) region, considering the significant impact of digital technology on modern government. It highlights the need for policies and platforms that strengthen local systems and preserve indigenous knowledge in the face of the digital revolution.

Given this context, the study investigated the following research questions to enhance comprehension of how digitalization affects conventional government and cultural conservation in South Africa and the SADC region:

What strategies can South Africa and SADC member states utilize to leverage digital technology in order to promote citizen engagement in governance while still respecting and preserving indigenous knowledge systems?

How can we create digital platforms that accurately represent and maintain the cultural diversity and legacy of the communities in South Africa and the Southern African Development Community (SADC) region? How can we apply Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH) principles to culturally align digital governance activities in South Africa and the SADC region? What strategies can South Africa and other SADC nations employ to oversee and assess the influence of digitalization on the safeguarding of indigenous knowledge and cultural values?

This paper point toward these concerns in order to provide a complete understanding of how digitalization affects the ever-changing governance landscape of South Africa and the SADC region. The ultimate goal is to provide practical and valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders involved in digital governance.

3. Literature Review

The governance legacy across African Countries, particularly South Africa, deeply influences approaches to digitisation and the preservation of local knowledge and values. These governance systems, often shaped by colonial histories and post-independence political dynamics, have resulted in diverse and complex frameworks for integrating traditional knowledge with modern digital systems. The South African government's policies, along with those of other African nations, are increasingly recognizing the importance of preserving cultural heritage and indigenous knowledge; through challenges remain in implementing these initiatives effectively (Agyemang & Dadzie, 2021).

One of the main challenges in digitising local knowledge in Africa is the uneven access to digital infrastructure. Rural areas in South Africa, for example, often lack reliable internet connectivity, which impedes efforts to digitise culture heritage. The absence of such infrastructure not only limits local communities' access to these digital resources but also threatens the sustainability of digitisation projects aimed at preserving their heritage (Nyamnjoh, 2020). Additionally, limited funding and technological resources further constraint the capacity of local governments and communities to manage digital preservation initiatives effectively (Chigona & Metfula, 2022).

The South African government has introduced policies, such as the National Development Plan (NDP), to address these issues by fostering digital inclusion and accessibility. However, critiques highlighting that these policies often overlook the importance of integrating cultural preservation explicitly within the scope of digital policies prioritise economic and infrastructural growth over the preservation of cultural heritage (Government of South Africa, 2019).

Community involvement is a crucial component in successful digitisation projects for preserving local knowledge. Research shows that projects that engage local stakeholders, including traditional leaders and community representatives, are more effective in capturing and preserving indigenous knowledge systems. This involvement not only ensures that digitisation efforts reflect community values but also fosters a sense of ownership, which is essential for the sustainability of these projects (Osei & Oduro-Frimpong, 2021). Community-based approaches are also critical in addressing the limitations imposed by formal governance structures which may not always be attuned to local cultural needs and practices (Chigona & Metfula, 2022).

International collaborations and funding have played a significant role in advancing digitisation initiatives across Africa. While foreign partnerships can provide essential resources and expertise, they also risk imposing external values on local knowledge systems, potentially compromising the culture relevance of the preserved knowledge. Studies on South Africa and neighbouring countries shows that locally driven projects are often more culturally sensitive and better aligned with indigenous values (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2023).

Emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and blockchain, present new possibilities for the preservation of local knowledge. AI, for instance, is being used to document and digitise indigenous languages and oral histories, ensuring their accessibility for future generations (Makalelo et al., 2022). Blockchain technology, on the other hand, offers a means of securely recording and authenticating indigenous knowledge, safeguarding it against unauthorised modifications and ensuring that it remains under the control of local communities (Okunola, 2023).

In South Africa, case studies of digitisation projects highlight the importance of balancing traditional governance insights with national policy frameworks. Rural communities, which often rely on traditional governance systems, may find some digital policies misaligned with their cultural needs. Consequently, integrating these traditional governance structures into digitisation strategies has proven essential for the preservation of local knowledge that genuinely reflects the values and practices of these communities (Maseko, 2021).

The complex fabric of communal deliberation, verbal narration, and ancient legal systems historically connect African governance. These systems emphasize the involvement of the community, with elders and traditional leaders playing crucial roles in the government process (Mengisteab 2019). Maserumule, (2011); Mustasilta (2019) examines the interplay between traditional governance and state governance in sub-Saharan Africa and how this interaction impacts the dynamics of peace and war. Integrating traditional

authority into public administration can effectively minimize the likelihood of armed conflict, in contrast to the scenario where they remain unrecognized by the state. Mengisteab (2019) emphasizes the existence of parallel institutions in African nations, where traditional systems, commonly found in rural regions, frequently coexist or clash with formal state laws, resulting in institutional inconsistency.

Within the realm of post-colonial governance, the use of digital technologies poses a contradictory and complex obstacle. While they provide instruments for improved communication and governance, they also pose a potential threat to the integrity of indigenous governing systems. Georgiadou et al. (2011) investigate the 'participatory sensing' projects in East Africa, which are examples of Digital Earth and seek to empower regular residents in government. Nevertheless, as Mann (2017) points out, the Big Data revolution frequently entails the retrieval of data from African organizations for examination in more developed nations, giving rise to concerns over data sovereignty and economic exploitation.

The influence of the digital era on traditional governance

The emergence of the digital era has brought about substantial changes in governance institutions throughout Africa. Obonyo and Muhumuza (2021) examine the simultaneous existence and absence of synchronization between traditional governance systems and local government reforms in Uganda, highlighting the difficulties this presents for local governance and the provision of services. Marrengane, et al. (2021) analyze the functions of traditional authority in African cities, specifically as guardians of community values and moral authorities, emphasizing their pivotal role in urban development. Digitalization has been hailed as a catalyst for development, improving government processes and encouraging the active participation of citizens. Baud et al. (2014) examine the profound impact of digital and geographic knowledge management on urban governance, highlighting the capacity to enhance urban planning through a knowledge-driven approach and enhance the competency of local government.

The integration of technology, into the conservation efforts of wisdom has presented both opportunities and challenges. Masenya (2022) points out that in rural areas Indigenous knowledge is mainly passed down through spoken traditions and the recollections of elders, which are at risk of being lost due to factors like mortality, illness and memory decline. Utilizing methods can ensure that this knowledge is not protected for future generations but also shared widely thus preserving cultural heritage. Similarly Winschiers Theophilus et al. (2013) suggest that mobile technologies can assist in conserving knowledge in settings by altering its presentation during the digital transformation process. However they emphasize the significance of design and local ownership to maintain an respectful preservation approach (Winschiers Theophilus et al., 2013). Additionally Chigwada and Ngulube (2023) highlight the role of librarians, in managing the convergence of technology and cultural traditions to uphold Indigenous knowledge in the digital realm (Chigwada & Ngulube 2023).

Preserving knowledge, in the age presents challenges when it comes to intellectual property rights. Obijiofor (2015) delves into the complexities of owning and preserving art, crafts and traditional practices in today's landscape. While new technologies and

globalization have boosted the visibility and connections of communities they have also sparked concerns about safeguarding their expressions and intellectual property rights (Obijiofor, 2015). In a vein Chigwada and Ngulube (2023) highlight the ethical dilemmas linked to documenting knowledge advocating for close collaboration between librarians and stakeholders with Indigenous communities to promote ethical preservation practices (Chigwada & Ngulube 2023). Additionally Benyei et al. (2020) propose that IT driven initiatives show promise for involving communities in conserving knowledge despite challenges faced by existing ex situ efforts (Benyei et al., 2020).

In summary safeguarding knowledge in the era necessitates a comprehensive approach encompassing digital preservation ethical documentation practices and respect, for intellectual property rights. While digital tools offer means of protecting and disseminating this knowledge their deployment must be managed thoughtfully to honor customs and engage Indigenous communities actively. By combining these initiatives we can help safeguard the endurance and strength of knowledge systems amidst transformations.

Application of Systems Theory and Critical Systems Heuristics in African Governance

Systems theory provides a comprehensive viewpoint for comprehending the complex interactions within governance organisations. Examining the thorny character of African government, which involves the coexistence and interaction of traditional and digital systems, is especially pertinent (Ulrich, & Reynolds 2010). Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH) is an analytical tool that evaluates systems by incorporating local knowledge and considering the ethical and cultural aspects of governance. It provides approaches for this purpose. In his work, Kalusopa (2018) offers a strategic perspective on the policy choices required to improve the conservation and accessibility of digital artifacts in Africa. Kalusopa (2018) emphasizes the importance of culturally and ethically informed digital governance solutions, aligning with the principles of CSH. Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH) is a useful technique for effectively managing the complexities of digital governance. Ulrich (2012) presents a framework that allows for a thorough evaluation of digital projects, ensuring that technology solutions are in line with cultural values and the specific local environment. Breuer & Lüdeke-Freund (2017) demonstrate how ICT-based participatory development initiatives can improve local government, aligning with the ideals of CSH.

Integration of different regions and the implementation of digital governance

The SADC region, comprising multiple countries in Southern Africa, encounters distinctive challenges and prospects in the domain of digital governance. A crucial element of this matter is the requirement for robust regional integration, which is indispensable for efficient digital governance. Samori, et al. (2023) emphasize the significance of integrating Fourth Industrial Revolution technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and modern biotechnology, to address development challenges and enhance digital governance in the region. Given South Africa's prominent position in the SADC area, this strategy is especially pertinent (Samori, et al. 2023).

South Africa, being a prominent participant in the Southern African Development Community (SADC), confronts distinct difficulties and prospects in the realm of digital governance. The nation is currently managing the complexities of merging conventional governance systems with contemporary digital technologies. A study by Ayamga, et al. (2023) explores how digitalization affects various sectors, including agriculture. Their findings shed light on how South Africa may utilize digital technologies to promote sustainable development and effective government. These activities are essential for South Africa to uphold its dominant position in the region (Ayamga, et al. 2023).

The implementation of digital governance in South Africa and the wider SADC area presents various difficulties, such as concerns regarding cybersecurity, digital literacy, and the necessity for efficient regional cooperation. Chinoda and Kapingura (2023) conducted research on the effects of digital financial inclusion and bank rivalry on bank stability in Sub-Saharan Africa, specifically South Africa (Union Africa, 2020). Their study emphasizes the importance of implementing strategic policies to improve digital governance. This entails tackling issues related to digital literacy, bridging infrastructure deficiencies, and cultivating a cooperative atmosphere that promotes digital transformation (Chinoda & Kapingura, 2023).

In conclusion, the preservation of local knowledge and values through digitisation in South Africa and other African contexts requires a nuanced approach that considers the influence of governance legacy, the involvement of local communities, as the thoughtful application of emerging technologies. While there are significant challenges, such as limited infrastructure and the risk of cultural misalignment in international partnerships, the progress made in recent years offers a foundation for developing sustainable, culturally sensitive digitisation initiatives that protect and celebrate African heritage.

4. Contextualisation framework

The integration of digitalization into post-colonial African governance structures offers a conceptual framework that prioritizes the preservation and improvement of indigenous knowledge systems while embracing contemporary technological breakthroughs. In order to undertake such a task, it is necessary to understand the social, cultural, and economic aspects that shape the African experience. Digital initiatives can enhance service delivery and civic involvement in resource-limited situations, such as those commonly seen in African towns. Osah and Pade-Khene (2020) offer valuable information on the creation of a comprehensive e-government strategy formulation framework that focuses on systems-oriented approaches. Local governance can effectively implement digital initiatives using this framework. Furthermore, Thinyane and Terzoli (2009) emphasize the importance of integrating indigenous knowledge into digital solutions. This approach, which focuses on knowledge and context, is crucial for effectively including marginalized people. Bert et al. (2015) highlight the difficulties presented by digital technology in dealing with complicated policy issues in various organizational settings. They stress the importance of adopting a systems theory approach to analyze the interactions among key individuals. In addition, Machiri and Pade-Khene (2020) examine the adoption of Digital Citizen Engagement (DCE) in the provision of local government services,

emphasizing the complex process of acquiring knowledge and implementing political reforms that are essential for the effective incorporation of information and communication technology (ICT) in governance.

Formulating policies for the development of digital libraries and archives

Diso (2012) emphasizes the crucial role of regional and national policies in fostering access to information for development. It underscores the importance of comprehensive policies that facilitate the establishment of digital libraries and archives. These activities are essential for the preservation and accessibility of African resources, as well as for promoting resource sharing at both the continental and global levels. Anderson and Christen (2013) propose an inventive system of licenses and labels for Indigenous peoples, which presents an alternative framework for intellectual property management of digital cultural heritage. This framework responds to the demand from Indigenous communities for approaches that diverge from Western legal norms and better address their distinct requirements. Bimbe et al. (2015) examine potential future situations for the exchange of information in Africa. They employ foresight approaches to analyze the potential effects of digitalization on the growth and fair allocation of knowledge by the year 2030. Their research offers vital insights into the future of knowledge dissemination in an ever-expanding digital African environment.

Conservation of Indigenous Knowledge in the Era of Digitalization

Concerns arise about conserving indigenous knowledge, which is inherently intertwined with cultural heritage, due to the shift towards digitalization. Thinyane and Terzoli (2009) discuss the difficulties of digital marginalization and stress the importance of developing digital solutions that incorporate local knowledge within the community. They promote a knowledge-focused strategy for digitalization, which is crucial for meaningful engagement in the worldwide information society. The advent of the digital era offers both a chance and a requirement to save local knowledge. Scholars have emphasized the significance of digitizing and incorporating indigenous knowledge systems into contemporary governance platforms to guarantee their continuity and relevance. Balogun and Kalusopa (2021) highlight the lack of digital preservation laws specifically designed for Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS) in South Africa and propose the implementation of a comprehensive framework to protect this knowledge. This paradigm encompasses both the technical components of digital preservation and the cultural considerations associated with managing Indigenous Knowledge Systems (IKS). In addition, Gregson et al. (2015) analyze the possible influence of digital technologies on development, specifically in sub-Saharan Africa. They highlight the importance of implementing measures that enhance the conservation and availability of digital resources, including local and indigenous knowledge.

Digital preservation of Indigenous knowledge is an increasingly critical in this contemporary period of globalization and advancing technology. Conserving this precious heritage is further underscored by its significant socio-economic benefits, which have been referred to as contributing to the attainment of sustainable development. According to Ghimire (2021), indigenous practices are instrumental in the optimal exploitation of natural resources; however, in technologically advanced societies, these practices are typically

overlooked. Digitalization provides a vital tool for the long-term preservation and worldwide accessibility of Indigenous knowledge, which is more urgent as the pressure that new technology and communication channels exert on such systems keeps getting thicker (Ghimire, 2021). Brodt (2001) emphasizes that already globalization and the scientisation of local management systems have been reducing the survival chances at central India's heart. Practical preservation will require knowledge of Indigenous knowledge systems, their adaptability, and connectedness, coupled with conservation strategies that maintain these systems in situ (Brodt, 2001).

The literature suggests a governance model that utilizes digital tools to empower communities, improve service delivery, and preserve the continent's cultural heritage in the digital era.

5. Research methodology

This paper employs a qualitative research methodology based on a constructivist paradigm. It aims to explore the complex relationship between digitalization, governance, and knowledge preservation in African contexts. The researcher conducted the research using a desktop research approach. This approach facilitates a comprehensive investigation of the phenomenon by actively involving many theoretical viewpoints and empirical evidence (Creswell & Poth, 2018). This paper seeks to comprehensively understand how combining ideas from various sources can strengthen traditional governance institutions and protect local knowledge systems using digital technologies.

6. Data Collection

The systematic literature search included a period of ten years, exploring databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, and African Journals Online (AJOL) in order to gather relevant studies. The collection consisted of peer-reviewed articles, policy documents, and conference proceedings that elucidated the intricacies of governance in the digital era and the conservation of indigenous knowledge in Africa. The rigorous inclusion criteria guaranteed examination of only the most relevant and influential research (Given, 2008).

7. Data Analysis

The researcher methodically employed Clarke, & Braun (2013) thematic analysis method to code the data and identify themes that align with the study's objectives. The analytical process underwent repeated refinement, using the interpretative insights of scholars such as Saldaña (2021) to assure the robustness and theoretical grounding of the findings. The theme narratives created offer a comprehensive depiction of the digitization of governance and the preservation of indigenous knowledge in African countries.

Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH) makes the research design in this paper much better by giving a full look at the complicated links between African countries' governance structures, the use of digital technologies, and the preservation of indigenous knowledge. CSH allows for a comprehensive examination of both the visible frameworks and the hidden elements, such as power dynamics, driving forces, and agendas, of the different

stakeholders who are leading the digitalization of governance systems in Africa (Midgley, 2000).

Implementing CSH in the context of this article entails adopting the twelve essential heuristic questions stated by Ulrich (2005), which function as a methodological guide. This inquiry examines the digital governance landscape from four perspectives: the reasons behind digital initiatives, the power dynamics that either support or hinder progress, the knowledge foundation that guides digital strategies, and the credibility of the transformative actions taken (Ulrich, 2005).

Table 1. Critical System Heuristics four (4) perspectives

4 CSH Perspectives	Details
Boundary Critique	Reasons behind digital initiatives
	Power dynamics
	Knowledge foundation
	Credibility of actions
Basis of Motivation	Sense of purposefulness
	Value comes from
Basis of Power	Who is in control
	Needed for success
Basis for Knowledge	Experience and expertise support
Basis for Legitimacy	Where legitimacy lies

Adapted from: Ulrich 2005,

During the process of analyzing data, this technique not only helps to identify repeating themes but also allows for a critical evaluation of the roles and influence of many actors, ranging from policymakers who shape digital strategies to the individuals who preserve local knowledge. During this comprehensive examination, the inequalities in power and the varying availability of digital resources may shape the understanding and discussion of governance in the African context (Córdoba & Midgley, 2006).

Moreover, CSH plays a crucial role in analyzing the process of conceptualizing digital strategies, their incorporation into local knowledge systems, and their resulting influence on society's values and norms. This paper advocates the use of CSH to design digital methods that are both technologically advanced and ethically and culturally conscious. This guarantees that digitalization activities align with the values and needs of African societies (Ulrich, 2005; McIntyre-Mills, 2006).

CSH investigates how digital technology can enhance the conservation of local knowledge and traditions. Adopting a critical perspective is essential for promoting a discussion that supports a fair and long-lasting digital future in Africa that respects and preserves its diverse indigenous knowledge and cultural legacy (McIntyre-Mills, 2006).

8. Findings and Results

This paper uncovers a complex interaction between traditional governance legacies and contemporary governance frameworks. Aboi (2022) examines the application of Plato's concepts of a just city and a just soul in the context of modern African leadership and societal issues. He proposes that the process of introspection and the revitalization of native concepts of authority are essential for attaining effective administration in Africa. This viewpoint emphasizes the necessity of governance models that are not just technologically sophisticated but also firmly grounded in cultural tradition. A dual focus is crucial for the development of government institutions that are durable and inclusive and that effectively connect with the general population (Aboi, 2022).

Regional integration refers to the “process of countries in a specific geographic area coming together to form closer economic and political ties” (Hertzenberg, 2011:8). In the context of digital governance, regional integration involves the coordination and harmonization of policies and regulations related to the digital sphere among countries in a particular region. This process aims to address the challenges and complexities that arise in governing digital technologies and services across borders.

The results suggest that the integration of different regions plays a crucial role in successfully implementing digital governance in the SADC region. As underlined by Samori, et al. (2023), the integration of Fourth Industrial Revolution technologies, including AI and modern biotechnology, is crucial for addressing development issues and increasing digital governance. This strategy is especially relevant for South Africa, given its significant influence in the SADC area. These findings indicate that in order to achieve overall success in digital governance in Southern Africa, it is essential to have deeper regional cooperation and integration of digital initiatives (Samori, et al. 2023).

The analysis highlights South Africa's distinctive role in spearheading digital governance projects in the SADC region. Studies such as those conducted by Ayamga, et al. (2023) indicate how South Africa may apply digitalization to encourage sustainable development and governance, serving as a model for other countries in the region. The presence of effective leadership is essential for successfully managing the integration of conventional governance systems with contemporary digital technology (Ayamga, et al 2023).

The findings additionally demonstrate that achieving digital transformation in South Africa and the SADC area necessitates overcoming a range of obstacles, such as cybersecurity vulnerabilities, limited digital literacy, and inadequate infrastructure. Chinoda and Kapingura (2023) emphasize the significance of strategic policy development in improving digital governance and stress the necessity for South Africa to successfully tackle these difficulties. The study promotes the implementation of policies that improve digital literacy and infrastructure, with the aim of creating a cooperative environment for digital governance (Chinoda and Kapingura, 2023).

The findings demonstrate that South Africa's leadership in digital governance is crucial for the progress of the SADC region. South Africa has the potential to take the lead in building strong and sustainable digital governance practices in the region by tackling

regional integration difficulties, utilizing technical breakthroughs, and effectively managing the intricacies of digital transformation.

The convergence of traditional governance systems and modern digital structures offers a distinct opportunity to improve the governance landscape in Africa. This paper shows how important Critical System Heuristics (CSH) and traditional ideas of governance are for creating governance models that recognize and use indigenous knowledge and practices. By preserving these legacies while embracing digital advancements, as evidenced in the digitization of the Vha-Venda oral tradition (Kugara and Mokgoatšana, 2022), African nations can develop governance systems that are not only effective but also culturally relevant and widely accepted by their citizens. This strategy is in line with the United Nations Development Programme's focus on inclusive participation, which is crucial for attaining Sustainable Development Goal 16 and promoting governance models that truly connect with the population (UNDP, 2021).

According to Lubinga, et al (2022), conducting comparative studies across different African regions could provide insights into how varied cultural settings impact the incorporation of digital and traditional government. Moreover, it is advisable to conduct longitudinal studies in order to evaluate the long-term viability and influence of digital governance initiatives on financial inclusion and economic growth (Chinoda and Kapingura, 2023). Regarding implementation, there is a strong focus on enhancing capabilities and creating digital platforms that are culturally sensitive. These platforms are crucial for preserving the authenticity of traditional practices in the digital realm (Mwangi, et al. 2022).

Nevertheless, the process of incorporating digital governance alongside traditional legacies has certain difficulties. Overcoming resource limits and technological impediments, such as poor internet access and digital literacy, is crucial. Collaborations with global organizations and the business sector can offer essential assistance to surmount these obstacles (Vermesan, et al 2022). Community participation and the modification of technology to meet local settings are also vital, ensuring that governance systems are relevant and effectively embraced by local communities (Shava,& Vyas-Doorgapersad, 2023).

To ensure the success of digital governance systems that include traditional legacies in Africa, it is crucial to address current resource and technological obstacles while also promoting community involvement and adapting technology to local circumstances. The long-term viability of a project will depend on the careful development of strategies, the enhancement of capabilities, ongoing monitoring and assessment, and the adoption of technical advancements. African states can establish governance structures that are sustainable, effective, inclusive, and culturally resonant by promoting collaborative innovation ecosystems (Samori et al., 2023; Bruce et al., 2023; Aguboshim et al., 2023). The effective execution of these methods holds the potential to establish digital governance in Africa as a paradigm of inclusiveness and sustainable progress.

Promoting Systems Thinking in South Africa's Development Agenda

The future trajectory for systems thinking in Africa, namely in South Africa, is strategically aligning systemic methodologies to promote sustainable development and

innovation. In their study, Nguyen et al (2023) analyzed the efficacy of South Africa's garment industry's innovation systems, highlighting the necessity for policy coherence and consistency. This study highlights the implementation of systems thinking in public policy to enhance sectoral systems of innovation, promoting economic growth and sustainability (Nguyen, et al 2023) .

Quacoe, and Kong,(2023) conduct a study that examines the relationship between sustainable development and innovation in South Africa, with a specific focus on green growth and entrepreneurship. The analysis utilizes the Quintuple Helix Innovation Model to shed light on the interconnectedness of these factors within the field of environmental sustainability. Their research findings affirm the idea that supporting entrepreneurship and green growth is essential for achieving sustainable development in South Africa. This underscores the importance of adopting a systems-thinking approach to tackle environmental concerns and stimulate innovation (Quacoe, and Kong, 2023). Ganson (2023) explores the concept of shared value as a means of shared power, specifically within the framework of corporate and economic development in South Africa. The study highlights the need for firms to participate in wider networks to achieve societal objectives, emphasizing the need to adopt a systemic approach to economic and social change. Implementing this strategy is crucial for tackling socio-economic inequalities and promoting comprehensive development in South Africa (Ganson, 2023).

The results of this study are contextually grounded in South Africa, which has a unique socio-political and cultural landscape shaped by a complex governance legacy, diverse ethnic groups, and a history of both colonial and post-colonial influences. This background influences how digital policies are adopted, as well as how local knowledge and values are preserved. Although these findings provide valuable insights for South Africa, generalising the results to other African countries or beyond requires caution. Each country possesses its own governance structures, digital readiness, and cultural dynamics, all of which affect that adoption and effectiveness of digitisation initiatives in knowledge preservation. For instance, governance legacy plays different roles in countries like Nigeria and Ghana, where local governments might face distinct challenges and opportunities for integrating indigenous knowledge within national frameworks (Agyemang & Dadzie, 2021).

The study's findings may hold broader relevance in countries with similar socio-political characteristics, such as those in sub-Saharan Africa that share a legacy of colonial governance structures. In these countries, similar constraints regarding infrastructure, funding, and policy alignment with indigenous cultural needs are prevalent. The need for community involvement, as highlighted in this paper, is shared requirement across many African nations that recognise the importance of local perspectives in governance and cultural preservation. Studies in countries such as Kenya and Zimbabwe have indicated that the inclusion of local communities significantly improves the sustainability and acceptance of digital preservation projects (Osei & Oduro-Frimpong, 2021). This similarity suggests that the study's findings may have applicability across African countries with parallel governance and cultural challenges, but further studies would be needed to confirm this generalisability.

However, extending these results to non-African contexts, such as Asian or Latin American countries, may be limited due to differing governance structures and digital

policies. For instance, countries like India and Brazil have unique digital policies. For instance, countries like India and Brazil have unique digital policies and infrastructure capabilities that influence their knowledge preservation strategies differently. While some principles, such as community involvement and the use of emerging technologies for knowledge preservation are universally applicable, the specific socio-cultural nuances and governance legacies must be considered. For a global application of these findings, future research should examine similar studies in diverse regions to compare the effectiveness of governance and digitisation strategies in knowledge preservation (Nyamnjoh, 2020; Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2023; Chigona & Metfula, 2022).

9. Conclusion

In Africa, especially South Africa, the forthcoming direction of systems thinking suggests a move towards a comprehensive approach encompassing economic development, environment sustainability, and social fairness. South Africa can lead the way in finding creative solutions to its various difficulties by integrating systems thinking with sustainable development goals Aigbavboa et al (2023). A comprehensive and unified approach is crucial for the progression of the SDG 2030 and Africa Agenda 2063. South Africa's choice to adopt systems thinking marks the beginning of an era, in development. This approach integrates environmental and social objectives with the aspirations of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Africa Agenda 2063. This alignment underscores South Africa's role in promoting governance and leveraging digitalization to empower society while safeguarding indigenous knowledge systems. South Africa serves as a model for the advancement of sustainability across the continent by advocating for governance frameworks particularly for women and youth.

The focus on innovation is in line with SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) and Aspiration 1 of the Africa Agenda 2063 emphasizing technology's role in driving economic growth and expanding access to education and information. By acknowledging the value of heritage as outlined in SDG 11 (Cities and Communities) and Aspiration 5 South Africa demonstrates how traditional wisdom can be combined with modern approaches to development. The merging of research findings presents an outlook for South African contingent upon successful implementation of these interconnected strategies and further investigation, into their tangible impacts.

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